

Introduction

In data science, we utilize various and diverse data to make informed decisions. In this project, we will explain the EDA, data manipulation, principles and techniques of data science from a computational and inferential thinking perspective. The following steps are involved:

1. Formulating the question or problem.
2. Finding and cleaning the data.
3. Exploratory data analysis.
4. Using prediction and inference to derive insights.

It is expected that further questions and problems will arise after the last step. At that point, we can go back to the steps again to discover any new characteristics in our problem. This positive iteration in our work is called the **data science lifecycle**.

If the data science lifecycle were easy, we wouldn't need project to explain it. Fortunately, each step presents different challenges that reveal new ideas, which serve as the basis for making well-informed decisions using data.

```
In [1]: # import necessary libraries
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
```

Data Students

The data science lifecycle consists of the following steps:

1. Formulating the Question or Problem:
 - What do we want to know or what problem do we want to solve?
 - What are the hypotheses?
 - What are our success metrics?
1. Finding and Cleaning the Data:
 - What data do we have available and what data are we looking for?
 - How can we gather more data?
 - How do we organize the data to start the analysis?
1. Exploratory Data Analysis:
 - Do we have data relevant to our problem?
 - Do the data contain biases, outliers, or other issues?
 - How do we transform the data to help us perform effective analysis?
1. Prediction and Inference:
 - What do the data tell us?
 - Did they answer the question or solve the problem?
 - What is the strength of our findings?

We will now experiment with these steps on a dataset of first names for Data students from previous semesters.

Formulating the Question or Problem: We want to know if the first names of the students provide us with additional information about them. Although the question may seem somewhat vague, it is enough to work with the available data and we can refine the question during our work to make it more precise.

Finding and Cleaning the Data: Let's start by taking a quick look at the available data. The data is a list of first names of students.

```
In [2]: data = pd.read_csv('Students.csv')
data
```

Out[2]:

	Name	Role
0	Keeley	Student
1	John	Student
2	BRYAN	Student
3	Kaylan	Student
4	Sol	Student
...
274	Sukhbir	Student
275	Nicholas	Waitlist Student
276	Ernesto	Waitlist Student
277	Athan	Waitlist Student
278	Michael	Waitlist Student

279 rows × 2 columns

We can quickly notice some issues in our data. For example, one of the students has their name written in all uppercase letters as BRYAN, and the meaning of the column "Role" is not clear. We also observe that the table contains two columns and 279 rows.

From this, we will learn how to identify and correct errors in our data. The difference in capitalization in the name "Bryan" will make the program consider BRYAN different from Bryan, but in reality, they are the same person. Therefore, we will convert all names to lowercase :

```
In [3]: data['Name'] = data['Name'].str.lower()
data
```

Out[3]:

	Name	Role
0	keeley	Student
1	john	Student
2	bryan	Student
3	kaylan	Student
4	sol	Student
...
274	sukhbir	Student
275	nicholas	Waitlist Student
276	ernesto	Waitlist Student
277	athan	Waitlist Student
278	michael	Waitlist Student

279 rows × 2 columns

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)

refers to the steps we take to understand the characteristics of the data and conduct subsequent analysis. Let's review student data:

```
In [4]: data.head(3)
```

Out[4]:

	Name	Role
0	keeley	Student
1	john	Student
2	bryan	Student

Now we have some questions. How many students are there? What does the "Role" column mean? We perform exploratory data analysis (EDA) to answer such questions.

How many students :

```
In [5]: print(f'There are {len(data)}, students')
```

There are 279, students

The number of students we have is 279. The next question is always: Does the data include all the students? In our case, the table includes all the students one semester.

What does the "Role" column mean? Let's explore the data in this column to understand its meaning.

```
In [6]: data['Role'].value_counts().to_frame()
```

```
Out[6]:
```

	Role
Student	237
Waitlist Student	42

In the previous table, we can see that the data not only includes students who studied the subject "Student", but also students who are on the waitlist in the "Waitlist Student" column. So, the "Role" column tells us whether the student enrolled in the subject or not.

What about the "Name" column? How can we explore it? A quick way to understand the "Name" column is by knowing the number of characters in each name:

```
In [7]: sns.distplot(data['Name'].str.len(),
                    bins=np.arange(12),
                    rug=True,
                    xlabel='Number of Characters')
plt.xlim(0,12)
plt.xticks(np.arange(12))
plt.ylabel('Proportion per caractere');
```

```
/Users/mu/opt/anaconda3/lib/python3.9/site-packages/seaborn/distributions.py:2619: FutureWarning: `distplot` is a deprecated function and will be removed in a future version. Please adapt your code to use either `displot` (a figure-level function with similar flexibility) or `histplot` (an axes-level function for histograms).
  warnings.warn(msg, FutureWarning)
/Users/mu/opt/anaconda3/lib/python3.9/site-packages/seaborn/distributions.py:2103: FutureWarning: The `axis` variable is no longer used and will be removed. Instead, assign variables directly to `x` or `y`.
  warnings.warn(msg, FutureWarning)
```


The previous chart tells us that the majority of names have a length between 4 and 8 characters. This helps us understand whether our data is reasonable or not. If there are a lot of one-character names, it would be a suitable reason to re-explore the data.

Although the data appears clear and simple, we will later discover how having only the first name can tell us a lot about our student population.

What's inside the Name column?

Does the first name of the student tell us anything about the subject?

We cleaned the data by converting all of it to lowercase. During exploratory data analysis, we noticed that we have about 280 students, some of whom have taken the subject and others who are on the waitlist. Most names range from 4 to 8 characters.

What can we learn about the students of the subject from their names? Let's take one name as an example:

```
In [8]: data['Name'][5]
```

```
Out[8]: 'jerry'
```

From this name, we can say that the name belongs to a male. We can also make an assumption about the age of the student. For example, if we know that the name "Jerry" was popular among children born in 1998, we can predict that the age of the student is in their twenties.

Thinking in this way led us to two questions:

- Can it tell us the names of the students regarding the distribution of males and females?
- Can it tell us the names of the students regarding the age distribution?

To answer these questions, we will need data that links names with gender and years. The Social Security Administration in the United

States has such data and it is available online at my [GitHub account](https://github.com/Muaeen/EDA) :<https://github.com/Muaeen/EDA>.

```
In [9]: babyname = pd.read_csv('babynames.csv')
babyname
```

```
Out[9]:
```

	Name	Sex	Count	Year
0	Mary	F	9217	1884
1	Anna	F	3860	1884
2	Emma	F	2587	1884
3	Elizabeth	F	2549	1884
4	Minnie	F	2243	1884
...
1891889	Titus	M	5	1883
1891890	Toney	M	5	1883
1891891	Verna	M	5	1883
1891892	Winnie	M	5	1883
1891893	Winthrop	M	5	1883

1891894 rows × 4 columns

The data contains the names, gender of the child, the number of children with this name, and the birth year of each child.

First, let's present the number of male and female births each year:

```
In [10]: pivot_year_name = pd.pivot_table(babyname, index='Year',
columns='Sex', values='Count',
aggfunc=sum)
pivot_year_name
```

```
Out[10]:
```

Sex	F	M
Year		
1880	90992	110491
1881	91953	100743
1882	107847	113686
1883	112318	104627
1884	129020	114443
...
2012	1756347	1892094
2013	1749061	1885683
2014	1779496	1913434
2015	1776538	1907211
2016	1756647	1880674

137 rows × 2 columns

```
In [11]: color = ["#E188DB", "#334FFF"]
with sns.color_palette(sns.color_palette(color)):
    pivot_year_name.plot(marker='.')
    plt.title("Registered Names vs Year Stratified by Sex")
    plt.ylabel('Names Registered that Year')
```


Determining Gender from Names

Let's use previous children's data to determine the number of males and females. As we did before, we start by converting all the letters in the children's data to lowercase:

```
In [12]: babyname['Name'] = babyname['Name'].str.lower()
babyname.sample(5)
```

```
Out[12]:
```

	Name	Sex	Count	Year
443584	suzanne	F	5609	1949
1348996	wardell	M	10	2000
169144	elgie	M	16	1920
772585	eustacia	F	8	1975
1223566	angelicia	F	9	1996

Then we gather the number of births for each name and the gender of the newborn.

```
In [13]: sex_count = pd.pivot_table(babyname, index='Name', columns='Sex', values='Count',
sex_count
aggfunc=sum, fill_value=.0, margins=True)
```

```
Out[13]:
```

Sex	F	M	All
Name			
aaban	0	96	96
aabha	35	0	35
aabid	0	10	10
aabir	0	5	5
aabriella	26	0	26
...
zyvon	0	6	6
zyyanna	6	0	6
zyyon	0	6	6
zzyzx	0	5	5
All	170639571	173894326	344533897

96175 rows × 3 columns

To determine whether a name is more common for male or female children, we can calculate the frequency ratio of the name for each gender:

```
In [14]: import ipywidgets as widgets
from ipywidgets import interact, interactive, fixed, interact_manual

def scroll(df, nr=7, nc=7):
    def peek(row=0, col=0):
        return df.iloc[row:row+nr, col:col+nc]
    if len(df.columns) <= nc :
        interact(peek,
                row=(0, len(df)-nr, nr),
                col=fixed(0))
    else :
        interact(peek,
                row=(0, len(df)-nr, nr),
                col=(0, len(df.columns), nc))
```

```
In [15]: prop_female = sex_count['F'] / sex_count['All']
sex_count['prop_female'] = prop_female
scroll(sex_count)
```

```
interactive(children=(IntSlider(value=0, description='row', max=96168, step=7), Output()), _dom_classes=('widg...
```

```
In [16]: sex_count.describe()
```

```
Out[16]:
```

	Sex	F	M	All	prop_female
count	9.617500e+04	9.617500e+04	9.617500e+04	96175.000000	
mean	3.548522e+03	3.616206e+03	7.164729e+03		0.633815
std	5.509654e+05	5.627054e+05	1.112335e+06		0.470597
min	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00	5.000000e+00		0.000000
25%	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00	1.100000e+01		0.000000
50%	1.100000e+01	0.000000e+00	4.600000e+01		1.000000
75%	1.030000e+02	2.500000e+01	2.410000e+02		1.000000
max	1.706396e+08	1.738943e+08	3.445339e+08		1.000000

```
In [ ]: df_copy = babyname.copy()
df_copy['predicted_sex'] = .apply(SexFromName)
```

```
In [51]: sex_count['prop_female'].nunique()
```

```
Out[51]: 8887
```

To determine that, we can define a function that searches for us whether the name is male or female using the previous ratio.

```
In [33]: def SexFromName(name):
    if name in sex_count.index:
        prop = sex_count.loc[name, 'prop_female']
        return 'F' if prop > 0.5 else 'M'
    else:
        return 'Name not in dataset'
```

Using the previous code snippet, can try any name and find out if the percentage of it being named as a male is higher than the percentage of it being named as a female.

Now, let's go back to the student data and add whether the student is male or female:

```
In [34]: data['Sex'] = data['Name'].apply(SexFromName)
data
```

```
Out[34]:
```

	Name	Role	Sex
0	keeley	Student	F
1	john	Student	M
2	bryan	Student	M
3	kaylan	Student	F
4	sol	Student	M
...
274	sukhbir	Student	Name not in dataset
275	nicholas	Waitlist Student	M
276	ernesto	Waitlist Student	M
277	athan	Waitlist Student	M
278	michael	Waitlist Student	M

279 rows × 3 columns

Now we can easily determine the number of males and females among our students.

Finding Age from Name

Using the same approach as before, we can find the distribution of age in our class by associating each name with the average years it has been repeated in:

```
In [19]: def avg_year(group):
    return np.average(group['Year'], weights=group['Count'])

avg_years = (
    babyname
    .groupby('Name')
    .apply(avg_year)
    .rename('avg_year')
    .to_frame()
)
```

```
avg_years
```

```
Out[19]:
```

	avg_year
Name	
aaban	2012.572917
aabha	2013.714286
aabid	2009.500000
aabir	2016.000000
aabriella	2013.884615
...	...
zyvion	2009.000000
zyvon	2015.000000
zyyanna	2010.000000
zyyon	2014.000000
zzyzx	2010.000000

96174 rows × 1 columns

In the same way as before, we can search for any name and find out the average year of birth.

```
In [23]: def year_from_name(name):
          return (avg_years.loc[name, 'avg_year']
                  if name in avg_years.index
                  else None)

data['Year'] = data['Name'].apply(year_from_name)
data
```

```
Out[23]:
```

	Name	Role	Year
0	keeley	Student	1998.147952
1	john	Student	1951.084937
2	bryan	Student	1983.565113
3	kaylan	Student	1998.587331
4	sol	Student	1948.074741
...
274	sukhbir	Student	NaN
275	nicholas	Waitlist Student	1988.055924
276	ernesto	Waitlist Student	1981.439873
277	athan	Waitlist Student	2004.397863
278	michael	Waitlist Student	1971.179231

279 rows × 3 columns

Now, we can easily display the distribution of years among the students:

```
In [24]: sns.distplot(data['Year'].dropna());
```

```
/Users/mu/opt/anaconda3/lib/python3.9/site-packages/seaborn/distributions.py:2619: FutureWarning: `distplot` is a deprecated function and will be removed in a future version. Please adapt your code to use either `displot` (a figure-level function with similar flexibility) or `histplot` (an axes-level function for histograms).
warnings.warn(msg, FutureWarning)
```


To calculate the average of the "Year" column, we do the following:

```
In [32]: data['Year'].mean()
```

```
Out[32]: 1983.846741800525
```

average age is 35 years (2018-1983=35), which is approximately twice the expected age for university students. Why do we see such high ages?

As a data scientist, you may come across results that we don't agree with or that contradict our expectations. The constant challenge we face is determining whether the surprising results are due to an error in our steps or a genuine error in the data. Since there is no easy way to guarantee accurate results, data scientists must have principles and rules to minimize finding incorrect results.

In this case, the only explanation for the unexpected result we encountered is that the most common names have been used for many years. For example, the name John is considered one of the most common names throughout history based on the data we obtained. We can confirm this by displaying a chart showing the number of children named John each year.

```
In [39]: names = babyname.set_index('Name').sort_values('Year')
jhon = names.loc['john']
jhon[jhon['Sex'] == 'M'].plot('Year', 'Count')
plt.title('Frequency of "John"');
```


It seems that the average age does not provide an accurate prediction of a person's age. But in some cases, the person's first name helps us with that, for example, when experimenting with the name Kanye, the following result appears:

```
In [40]: kanye = names.loc['kanye']
kanye[kanye['Sex'] == 'M'].plot('Year', 'Count')
plt.title('Frequency of "Kanye"');
```


Summary

In this project, quickly went through the data science lifecycle: forming the question or problem, finding and cleaning the data, exploratory data analysis, and inference and prediction.

The project and all Data in my Github account :<https://github.com/Muaeen/EDA>

```
In [ ]:
```